

ISic0015

I.Sicily inscription 0015

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 3515

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. M(arco) · Aurelio
2. Antonino · Caes(ari)
3. Imp(eratoris) · L(uci) · Septimi · Se
4. veri · Pii · Arabici · Adi
5. abenici · p(atris) · p(atriciae) · Aug(usti) · filio
6. res · p(ublica) · Panhor(mitanorum) · d(ecreto) · d(ecurionum)

Apparatus

Text of ILMusPalermo

Translation (en)

To Marcus Aurelius Antoninus (i.e. Caracalla), son of Emperor Lucius Septimius Severus Pius, victor in Arabia and Adiabene, Father of Fatherland, Augustus.
The citizens of Panhormus (erected this) by the decree of the city council.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491775

EDR 138097

EDCS 22000859

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7273 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650788>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 15

Raepsaet-Charlier, M.-Th. 1974. A propos du récent catalogue d'inscriptions latines du musée de Palerme. *Latomus*. 33: 124-127. At 125

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